

Analysis of the Influence of Price Perceptions, Product Quality and *E-WOM* on Purchasing Decisions at Shopee with Trust as Mediation

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Abstract:- This research aims to analyze the influence of price perceptions, product quality and E-WOM on purchasing decisions at Shopee with trust as mediation. This research is included in the type of quantitative research. The population in this research is Shopee User Students in Jakarta with a minimum of 1x shopping, with a sample size of 205 students. The data analysis method uses Structural Equation Model-Partial Least Square (SEM-PLS). The results of this research show that Product Quality and E-WOM have a positive and significant effect on Trust, but Price Perception has no effect on Trust. Meanwhile, Trust, Price Perception, and E-WOM have a positive and significant effect on Purchasing Decisions, but Product Quality has no effect on Purchasing Decisions. Trust is not able to mediate the relationship between Price Perception and Purchasing Decisions, but Trust is able to mediate the relationship between Product Quality as Full Mediation and E-WOM as partial mediation with Purchasing Decisions.

Keywords:- Price Perception, Product Quality, E-WOM, Trust, Purchasing Decisions, Shopee.

I. INTRODUCTION

Technology in Indonesia is developing very quickly, accompanied by developments in the business world. Technological developments have also influenced people's lifestyles. The presence of an increasingly sophisticated internet has an impact on technological progress. The use of the internet is not only as a medium of information and communication, but in modern life it can be used as a means of shopping (Ruri & Purnamawati, 2022). The number of Internet users in Indonesia reached 212.9 million as of early 2022. The number reached 77% of Indonesia's total population of 276.4 million. Of the 212.9 million internet users, 167 million of them use social media or the equivalent of 60.4% of the total population (Septiani, 2023).

In the last five years, Indonesian internet users have increased significantly. From 2018-2022 there was a significant increase, namely around 35.17%, which initially in 2018 had 132.7 million users, increasing to 204.7 million users at the beginning of 2022. This data can be seen in the following graph sourced from <https://databooks.katadata.co.id>:

Fig. 1: Number of Internet Users in Indonesia

The growth of e-commerce users is the impact of internet advances. E-commerce is the act of trading, transferring and exchanging products and information via the internet (Turban, 2012) in (Ruri & Purnamawati, 2022). The advancement of the internet has also become an opportunity for business people to develop their business with a strategy of providing online shop services (Nursyirwan & Ardaninggar, 2020) in (Oktavia et al., 2022)

Bank Indonesia (BI) has projected e-commerce transactions in November 2022 which are estimated to reach IDR 572 trillion (Sari, 2023). The following is data obtained from <https://www.similarweb.com/> regarding the number of visits to 5 e-commerce sites in Indonesia in the fourth quarter of 2022:

Fig. 2: The highest number of visits to the 5 E-Commerce sites in Indonesia

According to Ahdiat (2023a) , Shopee is the e-commerce with the most site visits in Indonesia throughout the fourth quarter of 2022. In October 2022 the number of Shopee visits was 179 million visits and then increased at the beginning of December 2022 to 191.6 million visits, resulting in an increase of 6.6%. The trend of increasing visits also occurred on the online shopping sites Lazada and Blibli, with details shown in the graph. Meanwhile, Tokopedia and Bukalapak's website visits have decreased, even though the numbers are relatively high and are in the top five nationally.

Shopee is an *e-commerce* or digital market platform with the largest number of users in Indonesia. Shopping online through Shopee is popular with many people because Shopee provides many features that support shopping activities. One of them is that Shopee provides a "bargain" feature which allows consumers to make price offers before checking out the goods they want to buy, so that consumers can get relatively cheaper prices. Then the choice of various delivery services such as JNE, Anteraja, J&T, Shopee Xpress becomes an attractive offer for Shopee users (Ruri & Purnamawati, 2022) .

However, based on data obtained from Similarweb (2023) , monthly report data shows that the total number of visits to the shopee.co.id website in February 2023 was 143.6 million visits and there was a decrease in the number of website visits by 16.18% since January 2023 and the decline occurred continuously until mid-March 2023. According to Bank Indonesia (BI), throughout 2022 the value of national e-commerce transactions will only reach

IDR 476.3 trillion, lower than BI's initial target of IDR 489 trillion. BI Deputy Governor Doni P. Joewono estimates that the transaction value fell from the target due to the easing of activity restrictions related to Covid-19, which then encouraged people to return to shopping at conventional stores.

Shopee needs to create a strategy to face increasingly fierce competition plus unstable economic conditions when Covid-19 will influence consumer decisions. Therefore, it is necessary to identify the factors that influence customer purchasing decisions. Where when the customer makes a purchasing decision, he is expected to make the right decision regarding the desired product.

Previous research has examined the factors that influence online purchasing decisions. Price perception is a factor that determines someone to make an online purchase (Agesti et al., 2021) . Mutiara & Wibowo (2020) stated that product quality is a factor that determines someone to make an online purchase. Nurhasanah et al. (2021) stated that E-WOM is a factor that determines someone to make online purchases. Rohmah (2021) states that trust is a factor that determines someone's ability to make online purchases. Fajrin & Gunadi (2022) stated that service quality is a factor that determines someone to make online purchases. Ruri & Purnamawati (2022) stated that convenience is a factor that determines someone to make purchases online.

Researchers conducted an online pre-survey via Google Docs to 30 respondents who had shopped at Shopee at least once.

Table 1: Researcher Pre-Survey Results

No	Variabel	Item Pernyataan	Hasil Survey	Persentase
1	Persepsi Harga	Saya melakukan pembelian via Shopee karena harganya murah, bersaing dan terdapat kesesuaian antara harga dengan kualitas & manfaat.	28	93,3%
2	Kualitas Produk	Saya melakukan pembelian via Shopee karena kualitas produk yang ditawarkan	26	86,7%
3	E-WOM	Saya mau berbelanja di Shopee karena ada informasi secara online oleh konsumen Shopee terkait produk (<i>E-Word Of Mouth</i>)	25	83,3%
4	Kepercayaan (<i>Trust</i>)	Saya melakukan pembelian via Shopee karena percaya terhadap aplikasi Shopee dan penjualnya	26	86,7%
5	Keamanan	Saya melakukan pembelian via Shopee karena keamanan dalam menggunakannya	24	80%
6	Promosi	Saya memutuskan berbelanja di Shopee karena ada promosi dari produk-produk yang ditawarkan	24	80%
7	Kualitas Pelayanan	Saya tertarik berbelanja di Shopee karena kualitas pelayanan yang baik (<i>Fast Response</i> , menjawab pertanyaan customer dengan baik)	20	66,7%
8	Kemudahan	Saya mau berbelanja di Shopee karena kemudahan dalam menggunakan aplikasinya	24	80%

Based on the background description above and supported by the data obtained, researchers are interested in conducting research with the title "Analysis of the Influence of Price Perception, Product Quality and E-WOM on Purchasing Decisions on Shopee with Trust as Mediation".

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Marketing

According to Kotler & Keller (2017) marketing The art and science of selecting target markets and attracting, retaining, and expanding a client base through the creation, provision, and dissemination of better customer value constitutes management.

The goal of Marketing is to know and understand the customer in such a way that the product or service suits the customer and then sells itself. Ideally, marketing should produce a customer who is ready to buy. All that is needed next is to provide that product or service (Kotler & Keller, 2017).

B. Theory of Reasoned Action

Ajzen and Fishbein (1980) assume that behavior is determined by the individual's desire to perform or not perform a certain behavior or vice versa. Desires are determined by two variables including attitudes and subjective norms (Mahyarni, 2013).

The Theory of Reasoned Action(TRA) explains that attitudes can influence behavior through a careful and reasoned decision-making process, and the impact is limited to three things, first, behavior is not determined much by general attitudes but by more specific attitudes.towards something, second, behavior is not only influenced by attitudes but by Third, attitudes toward a behavior combined with subjective norms to generate an intention or intention to behave in a specific manner. Subjective norms are our views about what other people expect us to do.(Witami & Suartana, 2019).

C. Consumer Behavior

The study of consumer behavior focuses on how people, groups, and organizations choose, pay for, utilize, and discard products, services, concepts, or experiences to fulfill their needs and desires. Accordingly, purchase decisions demonstrate how people, groups, and organizations choose, acquire, and use products, services, concepts, or experiences to fulfill their wants and aspirations.(Nurhasanah et al., 2021).

According to The American Marketing Association in Peter & Olson (2014), consumer behavior is the dynamic connection between consciousness, conduct, and the environment in which people interchange many facets of daily life. Put differently, consumer behavior encompasses both the acts and ideas people have during the consuming process. Recognizing dynamic consumer behavior that incorporates transaction and engagement is crucial.

D. Buying decision

Kotler & Keller (2017) defines a Purchase Decision as the formation of preferences by consumers for brands in a collection of choices. Consumers can also form intentions to purchase the most preferred brands. According to (Peter & Olson, 2014), The act of integrating knowledge to assess and select from among two or more alternative behaviors is known as consumer choice making. The process of integration yields a decision that indicates behavioral goals in a cognitive manner.

A purchasing decision is a consumer's final choice from several existing alternative choices (Hakim et al., 2021). Purchasing decisions can also be interpreted as buyers' decisions in choosing the brand to buy. A buyer or consumer can form the intention to purchase the most preferred brand (Warsito et al., 2022).

E. Price Perception

Price perception is the consumer's tendency to use price in evaluating products (Peter & Olson, 2014). According to Warsito et al. (2022), Price perception is the consumer's tendency to use price to assess the suitability of product benefits. Each individual's assessment of the price of a product's benefits is said to be expensive, cheap or moderate. It all depends on the individual's perception based on the environment and the individual's condition.

Based on this definition, price perception is the way consumers evaluate a product based on the benefits they will receive if they decide to buy it. So it has a strong influence on both buying interest and satisfaction.

F. Product quality

According to Moko et al. (2021), Product Quality is a combination of features that have the capacity to fulfill consumer desires and provide satisfaction to customers in accordance with the product's function and free from any deficiencies or defects. According to Kotler and Keller (2016) in Mutiara & Wibowo (2020), product quality is the ability of an item to provide results or performance that are appropriate or even exceed what customers want. The conclusion from this definition is that product quality is the ability of goods or services to provide satisfaction to consumers in accordance with expectations.

G. E-WOM

E-WOM is a product reference related to opinions and experiences from previous consumers which are shared via digital platforms (Khan et al., 2018). According to Cheung CMK, Lee MKO, Thadani DR (2009) in Nurhasanah et al. (2021) E-WOM is any statement—positive or negative—about a product or company that is accessible to a large number of individuals or organizations on the internet and is provided by actual customers, future customers, or customers who have used the product in the past.

Meanwhile, according to Litvin et al. (2008:461) in Ismagilova et al. (2017:17), E-WOM is all informal communication aimed at consumers via internet-based technology relating to the use or characteristics of certain goods and services, or their sellers.

H. Trust

Trust is a situation that occurs when a consumer believes in the integrity and honesty of the online website (Mutiara & Wibowo, 2020) . Meanwhile, according to Nurhasanah et al. (2021) , Consumers' confidence that the product can deliver on its stated value and brand intention, which is predicated

on their perception of the brand's ability to prioritize, give rise to brand trust, also known as brand dependability.

Based on these theories, the framework for this research is as follows:

Fig. 3: Framework of Thought

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This research uses quantitative methods with the Partial Least Square Structural Equation Model (PLS SEM) approach. The statistical tool used to test this research hypothesis is the Partial Least Square (Smart-PLS) program version 3.0. Data will be analyzed with two models. Measurement Model (Outer Model) is a measuring model that links hidden variables to indicators. A structural model that links latent variables is called an inner model or structural model.

The variables used in this research are Price Perception (X1), Product Quality (X2), E-WOM (X3), Trust (Z), and Purchase Decision (Y). In this study, purposive sampling

combined with non-probability sampling is the method used to collect data. A questionnaire with a Likert scale will be given to respondents located in Jakarta as Shopee users with the criteria of using it at least once.

IV. RESULTS

A. Evaluation of the Measurement Model (Outer Model)

It is possible to say that the outer model can specify the relationship between the latent variable and its indicators, or that this model explains how each indicator is connected to its hidden variable. Examining the construct reliability, discriminant validity, and convergent validity values is how the outer model is implemented.

Fig. 4: Path Diagram Outer Loading

➤ Convergent Validity Test Results

Convergent Validity testing is the loading factor value on the latent variable with its indicators. This measurement is carried out to test the validity of each variable. Data is said to be valid if it obtains a loading value > 0.5. Based on the path diagram of the measurement model in Figure 4, it states that all indicators for each variable have an outer loading / factor loading value of more than 0.5, which means all

indicators are valid. Thus, the research model has met the requirements for convergent validity, which means that all indicators are valid in measuring the construct.

The convergent validity test can also be done by looking at the AVE (*Average Variance Extracted*). It is declared that the construct meets convergent validity if the construct's AVE value is more than 0.5.

Table 2: AVE Value Results

Variabel	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)	Keterangan
Persepsi Harga	0,527	Valid
Kualitas Produk	0,558	Valid
E-WOM	0,524	Valid
Kepercayaan	0,551	Valid
Keputusan Pembelian	0,519	Valid

The table shows that all variables have an AVE value of more than 0.5, so it can be concluded that all variables have met discriminant validity (Ghozali & Latan (2019:37).

One way to test discriminant validity is through the Heterotrait-Monotrait Ratio (HTMT) test. The recommended HTMT value should be smaller than 0.85 (Clark & Watson 1995; Kline 2011) while others suggest a value smaller than 0.90 (Gold et al. 2001; Teo et al. 2008).

➤ Discriminant Validity Test Results

Table 3: HTMT Test Results

	E-WOM	Kepercayaan	Keputusan Pembelian	Kualitas Produk	Persepsi Harga
E-WOM					
Kepercayaan	0.714				
Keputusan Pembelian	0.596	0.707			
Kualitas Produk	0.801	0.682	0.651		
Persepsi Harga	0.475	0.535	0.680	0.881	

Based on the results of the HTMT test, it shows that all constructs have an HTMT value of less than 0.90. Thus, it can be stated that all constructs are valid in terms of discriminant validity.

square root of average variance extracted (AVE) value for each construct with the correlation between the construct and other constructs in the model. The results of the discriminant validity test based on the Fornell Lackers test were obtained as follows:

The discriminant validity test can also be carried out using the Fornell and Larcker method by comparing the

Table 4: Fornell and Larcker Test Results

	E-WOM	Kepercayaan	Keputusan Pembelian	Kualitas Produk	Persepsi Harga
E-WOM	0.724				
Kepercayaan	0.603	0.743			
Keputusan Pembelian	0.510	0.614	0.721		
Kualitas Produk	0.635	0.578	0.563	0.747	
Persepsi Harga	0.350	0.405	0.497	0.622	0.726

The results obtained were that each construct had a value greater than the correlation between one construct and the other constructs in the model. Thus, it can be stated that all constructs are valid in terms of discriminant validity.

➤ Reliability Testing Results

Good reliability or a questionnaire used as a reliable and consistent research tool if the composite reliability value is more than 0.70 (Hair, et al, 2016) in (Sihombing & Arsani, 2022) .

Table 5: Reliability Test Results

Variabel	Composite Reliability	Keterangan
Persepsi Harga	0,767	Reliabel
Kualitas Produk	0,862	Reliabel
E-WOM	0,868	Reliabel
Kepercayaan	0,895	Reliabel
Keputusan Pembelian	0,883	Reliabel

The results show that all research variables have a composite reliability value of more than 0.7, meaning that the data is reliable and can be tested on the inner model.

B. Structural Model Evaluation (Inner Model)

Inner model testing can be seen through the coefficient of determination R-Square (R²), effect size (F²), and Q-Square predictive relevance (Q²). Meanwhile, the

significance level of the path coefficient is used for hypothesis testing, namely predicting the relationship between latent variables.

➤ **R-Square Value Test Results (R²)**

The coefficient of determination R Square (R²) shows how much the exogenous variable explains the endogenous variable.

Table 6: R Square Value (R²)

Variabel Endogen	R Square (R ²)	Kriteria
Kepercayaan	0,434	Moderate/Sedang
Keputusan Pembelian	0,476	Moderate/Sedang

The results explain that Price Perception, Product Quality, and E-WOM simultaneously moderately influence the Trust variable, namely 0.434 (43.4%) while the remaining 56.6% is influenced by other factors outside the model. Meanwhile, Price Perception, Product Quality, E-WOM, and Trust simultaneously moderately influence the Purchase Decision variable, namely 0.476 (47.6%) while the

remaining 52.4% is influenced by other factors outside the model.

➤ **Effect Size Test Results**

Effect size or F² is used to find out how much the exogenous latent variable can support the endogenous latent variable.

Table 7: Effect Size Value (F²)

Variabel Eksogen	Variabel Endogen	
	Kepercayaan	Keputusan Pembelian
Persepsi Harga	0,012	0,056
Kualitas Produk	0,048	0,013
E-WOM	0,171	0,015
Kepercayaan	-	0,152

The Price Perception variable on Trust has an F² value of 0.012 ≤ 0.02, which means that Price Perception has no influence on Trust. Meanwhile, Price Perception on Purchasing Decisions has an F² value of 0.056 > 0.02, which means that Price Perception has a small influence on Purchasing Decisions. The Product Quality variable on Trust has an F² value of 0.048 > 0.02, which means that Product Quality has a small influence on Trust while Product Quality on Purchasing Decisions has an F² value of 0.013 ≤ 0.02, which means that Product Quality does not influence on Purchasing Decisions. The E-WOM variable on Trust has an F² value of 0.171 > 0.15, which means that

E-WOM has a moderate influence on Trust while E-WOM on Purchasing Decisions has an F² value of 0.015 ≤ 0.02, which means that E -WOM does not influence purchasing decisions. The variable Trust in Purchasing Decisions has an F² value of 0.152 > 0.15, which means that Trust has a moderate influence on Purchasing Decisions.

➤ **Predictive Relevance Test Results (Q²)**

Q² model value of more than 0 indicates the model has good predictive relevance, while a Q² value of less than 0 indicates the model lacks predictive relevance.

Table 8: Predictive Relevance Value (Q²)

Variabel Endogen	Q Square Predictive relevance (Q ²)	Keterangan
Kepercayaan	0,230	Memiliki nilai predictive relevance yang baik
Keputusan Pembelian	0,225	Memiliki nilai predictive relevance yang baik

It was found that the endogenous variable Trust has a Q^2 value of 0.230 and the endogenous variable Purchase Decision has a Q^2 value of 0.225. The calculation results show that the predicted relevance value (Q^2) for both endogenous variables is more than 0, so that the model can be said to have a relevant predictive value or a fit model or worthy of hypothesis testing.

➤ *Hypothesis test*

PLS-SEM analysis hypothesis testing in this study uses one-way hypothesis testing with a significance of 5% or with an error tolerance of $\alpha = 0.05$. The decision making in PLS-SEM analysis for the one-way hypothesis with a 5% significance test is if the $|t\text{-statistic}| > 1.645$ or significance value ($p\text{-value}$) < 0.05 and positive path coefficient value.

Fig. 5: Path Diagram Path Coefficient & T-Statistics Structural Model (Inner Model)

Based on this model, the direct hypothesis testing that is accepted is H2, H3, H4, H5, H7. Meanwhile, the

hypotheses that were rejected were H1 and H6. The following results are presented in table form:

Table 9: Results of Direct Hypothesis Testing

Hipotesis	Hubungan Jalur	Original Sample (Path Coeff)	T Statistics	P Values	Keterangan
H1	Persepsi Harga -> Kepercayaan	0,104	1,490	0,068	Ditolak, Data Tidak Mendukung
H2	Kualitas Produk -> Kepercayaan	0,256	2,611	0,005	Diterima, Data Mendukung
H3	E-WOM -> Kepercayaan	0,404	4,595	0,000	Diterima, Data Mendukung
H4	Kepercayaan -> Keputusan Pembelian	0,375	5,247	0,000	Diterima, Data Mendukung
H5	Persepsi Harga -> Keputusan Pembelian	0,220	3,153	0,001	Diterima, Data Mendukung
H6	Kualitas Produk -> Keputusan Pembelian	0,131	1,272	0,102	Ditolak, Data Tidak Mendukung
H7	E-WOM -> Keputusan Pembelian	0,123	1,701	0,045	Diterima, Data Mendukung

Then here is the mediation hypothesis testing table:

Table 10: Mediation Hypothesis Testing Results

Hipotesis	Hubungan Jalur	Original Sample (Path Coeff)	T Statistics	P Values	Keterangan
H8	Persepsi Harga -> Kepercayaan -> Keputusan Pembelian	0,039	1,385	0,083	Ditolak, Data Tidak Mendukung
H9	Kualitas Produk -> Kepercayaan -> Keputusan Pembelian	0,096	2,050	0,020	Diterima, Data Mendukung
H10	E-WOM -> Kepercayaan -> Keputusan Pembelian	0,151	3,899	0,000	Diterima, Data Mendukung

The results showed that in testing the mediation hypotheses that were accepted were H9 and H10, while H8 was rejected.

V. DISCUSSION

A. H1: Effect of Price Perception on Trust

H1 in this study is rejected or the data does not support the hypothesis. These results are not in accordance with research by Zulhelmi & Santoso (2018) and Humam et al. (2022), where there is no positive and significant influence between price perception and trust.

This shows that although price is a variable that is often considered sensitive in selecting a product, it did not occur significantly in this study. When Shopee applies low prices with a variety of services, it does not mean that it increases the level of consumer confidence in buying products on Shopee because other e-commerce competitors also apply competitive prices.

B. H2: Effect of Product Quality on Trust

H2 in this study is accepted or the data supports the hypothesis. These results are in accordance with research by Irfan et al. (2022) and Humam et al. (2022), where there is a positive and significant influence between product quality and trust. When product quality improves, consumer confidence will also increase. This is also in accordance with theory, the higher the level of product quality that satisfies consumers, the higher consumer trust will be (Kotler and Armstrong, 2012) in (Irfan et al., 2022).

C. H3: The Effect of E-WOM on Trust

H3 in this study is accepted or the data supports the hypothesis. These results are in accordance with research by Ranti et al. (2023) and Ihsan et al. (2022), where there is a positive and significant influence between E-WOM and trust. Customers can collect information about a product and evaluate it before buying so that this can increase trust. The better the information obtained through Electronic Word of Mouth, the higher the trust in Shopee.

D. H4: The Influence of Trust on Purchasing Decisions

H4 in this study is accepted or the data supports the hypothesis. These results are in accordance with the research of Wiraandryana & Ardani (2021) and Rohmah (2021), where there is a positive and significant influence between trust and purchasing decisions. This shows that online transactions involve certainty and asymmetric information. Therefore, there must be mutual trust between sellers and buyers (Katawetawaraks and Wang, 2011) in (Rohmah, 2021). With the rise of internet crime, such as credit card theft and fraud, the trust factor has become very important in online shopping transactions. This concept of trust means that buyers believe in the reliability of online sellers who can guarantee the security of online transactions.

E. H5: The Influence of Price Perceptions on Purchasing Decisions

H5 in this study is accepted or the data supports the hypothesis. These results are in accordance with research by Agesti et al. (2021) and Humam et al. (2022), where there is an influence of price perception on purchasing decisions.

Price perception is related to how price information is understood in its entirety and provides deep meaning to consumers, while purchasing decisions are the decision-making stage where consumers actually buy a product (Tjiptono, 2012: 193) in (Agesti et al., 2021). This shows that if there is an increase in price perception for products on Shopee, it will influence consumer purchasing decisions.

F. H6: The Influence of Product Quality on Purchasing Decisions

H6 in this study was rejected or the data did not support the hypothesis. These results are not in line with research by Oktavia et al. (2022) and Jannah & Arifin (2023) but in accordance with research by Ruri & Purnamawati (2022). This shows that the products sold by e-commerce Shopee have relatively the same quality as products sold by other e-commerce, so consumers assume that when shopping using any e-commerce there is no difference between the quality of products sold by e-commerce one with another.

G. H7: The Influence of E-WOM on Purchasing Decisions

H7 in this study is accepted or the data supports the hypothesis. These results are in accordance with research by Nurhasanah et al. (2021) and Pramesti et al. (2022). This shows that the better the product reviews, the more people decide to buy products on Shopee. E-WOM is useful because communication between humans is related to advantages or experiences when purchasing or using a product or service to make purchasing decisions.

H. H8: Trust Mediates the Relationship Between Price Perceptions and Purchase Decisions

H8 in this study was rejected or the data did not support the hypothesis. These results are not in accordance with the research of Irfan et al. (2022) and Suhaily & Darmoyo (2017) which show that price perception has a positive and significant effect on purchasing decisions through consumer trust.

As the results of the decision hypothesis H5 state that price perceptions have a significant influence on purchasing decisions, the effect of the trust variable in mediating the relationship between price perceptions and purchasing decisions is unmediated or no mediation. This is because without involving trust as a mediator variable, the price perception variable can directly influence purchasing decisions.

I. H9: Trust Mediates the Relationship Between Product Quality and Purchasing Decisions

H9 in this study is accepted or the data supports the hypothesis. These results are in accordance with research by Irfan et al. (2022) and Suhaily & Darmoyo (2017). As the results of the decision hypothesis H6 state that product quality has no significant effect on purchasing decisions, the effect of the trust variable in mediating the relationship between product quality and purchasing decisions is full mediation. This is because the product quality variable is significantly unable to influence purchasing decisions without the trust variable. However, through the trust variable, the product quality variable can significantly influence purchasing decisions.

J. H10: Trust Mediates the Relationship Between E-WOM and Purchase Decisions

H10 in this study is accepted or the data supports the hypothesis. These results are in accordance with research by Wiraandryana & Ardani (2021) and Ihsan et al. (2022). As the results of the decision hypothesis H10 state that E-WOM has a significant effect on purchasing decisions, the effect of the trust variable in mediating the relationship between E-WOM and purchasing decisions is partial mediation. This is because, whether through or without the trust variable, the E-WOM variable directly has a significant influence on purchasing decisions.

VI. CONCLUSION

A. Conclusion

The conclusions from this research are:

- Price Perception has no significant effect on Trust
- Product quality has a positive and significant effect on trust
- E-WOM has a positive and significant effect on Trust
- Trust has a positive and significant effect on purchasing decisions
- Price perceptions has a positive and significant effect on purchasing decisions
- Product quality has no significant effect on purchasing decisions
- E-WOM has a positive and significant effect on purchasing decisions
- Trust does not mediate the relationship between Price Perception and Purchasing Decisions. So the effect of the Trust variable in mediating the relationship between Price Perception and Purchasing Decisions is no mediation
- Trust mediates the relationship between Product Quality and Purchasing Decisions. So the effect of the Trust variable in mediating the relationship between Product Quality and Purchasing Decisions is full mediation.
- Trust mediates the relationship between E-WOM and purchasing decisions. So the effect of the Trust variable in mediating the relationship between E-WOM and Purchasing Decisions is partial mediation.

B. Suggestion

➤ For Companies (Shopee)

Shopee must continue to pay attention to the suitability of the prices given to the quality of the products themselves, with the aim of ensuring that consumers remain satisfied when buying goods offered by Shopee. Shopee also needs to pay attention to characteristics that are not found in other marketplaces. Customer service and input must also be given more attention, especially responding to consumers who give unfavorable reviews. Then Shopee also needs to provide services, especially the promises they have made to sellers

➤ For Further Researchers

Based on the results of R Square, the role of Purchasing Decisions as a dependent variable is 0.476 (47.6%) while the remaining 52.4% is influenced by other factors outside the model which were not examined in this research. Future

researchers are expected to be able to use other variables which are expected to have a greater influence on purchasing decisions such as security, promotion, service quality, convenience, etc.

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